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REPORT 2

PRESENTATION ANNUAL
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How Voters' Multiple Identities Affect their Response to Politicians' Moral Violations

Annemarie Walter and David Redlawsk

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Voters' Multiple Identities

- A social identity is a subjective sense of belonging to a group and an important part of people's self concept
- Social identities are acquired through inheritance, life experiences or accomplishment
- Social identities differ in internalization, i.e. the extent that they are central to people's self-concept

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Maintaining a Positive Social Identity

- Mechanisms include biased information processing, in-group favoritism and out-group derogation in behaviours
- In-group bias is moderated by identification strength
- Social groups have their own moral principles, and a group member transgressing these threatens the group image
- People's own morality as well as judgements about other people's morality is determined by their social identity

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Partisan Identity

- Partisanship and strength affects how voters perceive and respond to politicians' moral violations
- **Partisan Ingroup Bias Hypothesis (H1):** People will evaluate politicians engaged in moral violations who belong to their party (ingroup) more positively than politicians who do not (outgroup)
- **Partisan Identity Strength (H2):** The stronger people identify with their party, the greater their ingroup bias when evaluating politicians involved in moral violations

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Moral Principles of the Group

- Political parties have their own moral principles
- Moral Foundation Theory (MFT) suggests that liberals and conservatives have differing emphases, which may then be reflected accordingly in the two U.S. parties
- Liberals (Democrats) are more likely than conservatives (Republicans) to endorse the Care and Fairness principles, but generally do not endorse the Loyalty, Authority and Sanctity
- **Ingroup Moral Principles Violation (H3):** People will evaluate politicians that belong to their party (ingroup) more negatively when they violate moral principles of their ingroup than when ingroup politicians violate moral principles of the other party

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Moral Identity

- Moral identity entails the extent to which people's self-concept is organized around their moral beliefs
- People who hold a strong moral identity are more likely to interpret situations in a moral manner and act accordingly
- Moral identity mitigates in-group favoritism and out-group hostility
- **Moral Identity Strength Hypothesis (H4):** The stronger people's moral identity the more negatively they evaluate ingroup politicians involved in moral transgressions

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Experimental Design

- A vignette study using a between-subjects experiment in a 6 x 3 design embedded in a survey questionnaire administered to approximately 3000 U.S. voters and 3000 English voters
- We manipulated the moral principle violated (Care, Fairness, Loyalty, Authority and Sanctity) and added a social norm violation as a baseline
- We manipulated the partisanship of the politician (Republican, Democrat, no partisanship) in the vignette
- Data were collected between 2 October and 3 November 2020 by Dynata
- Dependent variable Likeability, 7-points scale running from 1 (Unlikeable) to 7 (Likeable)

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Stimulus Material

Norm violated	Vignette (non-partisan)
Care	You see a politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems.
Fairness	You see a politician making sure that those who voted for him get first access to jobs.
Loyalty	You see a politician in your town say the neighboring town is better.
Authority	You see a politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police at a disaster.
Sanctity	You see a politician was found having sex with a teenager.
Social	You see a politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol in a plastic grocery bag

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Results: Hypothesis 1

- **Partisan Ingroup Bias Hypothesis (H1):** People will evaluate politicians engaged in moral violations who belong to their party (ingroup) more positively than politicians who do not (outgroup)

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Effects of Shared Partisan Identity

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Results: Hypothesis 2

- **Partisan Identity Strength (H2):** The stronger people identify with their party, the greater their ingroup bias when evaluating politicians involved in moral violations

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Effects of Partisan Identity Strength

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Results: Hypothesis 3

- **Ingroup Moral Principles Violation (H3):** People will evaluate politicians that belong to their party (ingroup) more negatively when they violate moral principles of their ingroup than when ingroup politicians violate moral principles of the other party

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Effects of Ingroup Moral Principles

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Results: Hypothesis 4

- **Moral Identity Strength Hypothesis (H5):** The stronger people's moral identity the more negatively they evaluate in-group politicians involved in moral transgressions

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Results: Hypothesis 4

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Results: Hypothesis 5

- **Moral Identity Strength Hypothesis (H5):** The stronger people's moral identity the more negatively they evaluate ingroup politicians involved in moral transgressions

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Effects of Moral Identity

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Conclusions

- Both partisan identity as well as moral identity matter to how voters respond to moral violations
- We need to consider voters' multiple social identities when examining voters' moral judgments
- Limitations:
 - Only two social identities examined
 - Only measure positive partisan identity
 - Measure party's ingroup principles

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